

Synthesis of a series of aldol compounds by direct LDA reaction from pyruvaldehyde dimethyl acetal and 3-arylmethylidene pentane-2,4-diones by Knoevenagel reaction

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A new convenient synthesis of aldol compounds starting from pyruvaldehyde dimethyl acetal has been described. This method conveniently led to the synthesis of some biologically important compounds^{1,2}. A new synthesis of 3-arylmethylidene pentane-2,4-diones is reported via usual Knoevenagel condensation which has a significant role in synthesizing different sensors for metal cations or anions.

Keywords: Benzazoles, azoles, single step reaction, room temperature reaction, sensor application.

Introduction

There are many reports for the study of the aldol reaction of pyruvaldehyde dimethyl acetal by organocatalyzed enantioselective enamine type reactions¹⁻⁸. PEP (Phosphoenolpyruvate) and aldolase mimicry are essential for a direct organocatalytic entry for biomolecules of huge importance in chemical, biological and medicinal fields. In the key aldol reaction, the dimethyl acetal of pyruvic aldehyde is used as phosphoenolpyruvate (PEP) equivalent. In this communication, we report our results of an investigation of the same reaction under LDA reaction condition.

In this manuscript, we have reported the synthesis of the aldol products (**1a-1c**) from pyruvaldehyde dimethyl acetal with benzaldehyde, 3-pyridylaldehyde, 2-nitrobenzaldehyde in LDA. The yield of the reaction is low because of the formation of the unsaturated analogue of the products in such a strong basic condition (Scheme 1). We have also synthesized the products **2a-2f** by Knoevenagel reaction conditions. The product molecules have the biological activity in both

Scheme 1. Aldol reaction of pyruvaldehyde dimethyl acetal with different aldehydes for the synthesis of compounds (**1a-1c**).

cases, **2a-2f** can act as good precursors for the active sensor molecules for transition metals. These compounds can be further converted into new heterocyclic compounds, or they (**1a-1c** or **2a-2f**) can be functionalized more to synthesize new receptor molecules for recognition studies.

Results and discussion

In recent years many useful chemical and enzymatic methodologies have been reported and implemented to develop efficient synthesis of desired aldol products as well as of certain analogs^{9,10}. However, in enzyme-catalyzed reac-

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tions, the loss of stereo-control regarding the substrate scope is often a problem¹¹, and the total synthesis approaches have suffered from long reaction sequences¹² due to protecting group manipulations. Consequently, the need for short and practical synthetic routes remained a challenging endeavor of great interest as proven by the most recent achievements^{13–15}. Knoevenagel condensation is one of the most important reactions in organic synthesis for carbon-carbon bond formation¹⁶. This reaction is highly useful for the synthesis of functionalized enones and enolates, since addition reaction of the methylene components, activated with two electron withdrawing groups. The reaction has been used widely for the preparation of coumarin derivatives which are very important intermediates in cosmetics, perfumes and pharmaceutical industry¹⁷. There has been a growing interest in Knoevenagel products because many of them have significant biological activity. Among them, tyrphostin, such as α -cyanothiocinnamide were shown to inhibit autophosphorylation of the EGF-receptor, in addition to possessing antiproliferative effects on human keratinocytes. Knoevenagel condensations are usually catalyzed by different weak bases like ethylenediamine, piperidine or corresponding ammonium salts, DMAP or amino acids such as glycine, alanine and L-proline and is also reported with potassium fluoride, ionic liquids, calcite, triphenyl phosphine, natural phosphate, resin and montmorillonite KSF. However, it can also be performed using solid support catalysts. In this study, the Knoevenagel products **2a-2f** are formed by reaction of acetylacetone with 2-chlorobenzaldehyde, 2-bromobenzaldehyde, 3-pyridylaldehyde, 1-pyrenealdehyde, 2-quinoxaline-carbaldehyde and anthracene-9-carbaldehyde respectively, using proline in

Scheme 2. Synthesis of different Knoevenagel products (α -arylmethylidene- β -diketones) from acetylacetone (**2a-2f**).

DMSO^{18–27}. Thus a new facile synthesis of a series of 3-arylidene-pentane-2,4-dione including hetero arylidene pentane-2,4-dione under mild condition has been achieved.

Among the Knoevenagel products, **2d** is reported previously by Goswami *et al.*¹⁸. However, the crystal structure is new and is shown here which further confirms the structure.

Objectives for the synthesis of Aldol products and α -arylmethylidene β -ketones:

As Goswami *et al.* also work for molecular recognition area, the products **2a-2f** are very good precursors for making host materials for different transition metals. From compound **2d**, we have already synthesized a very good fluorescence probe¹⁸ for copper cation and fluoride anion. The final receptor BMPA was synthesized from the reaction of compound **2d** with 2-aminophenol. We are also in the process of making new sensors for the different analogues of this series as quinoxaline, anthracene and 3-pyridyl moieties. Those compounds may also play a very good role for making UV and fluorescence sensing precursors.

Experimental

General experimental:

All chemicals and solvents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals Private Limited and were used without further purification. Melting points were determined on a hot-plate melting point apparatus in an open-mouth capillary and are uncorrected. For NMR spectra, CDCl_3 was used as a solvent with TMS as an internal standard. Chemical shifts are expressed in δ units and ^1H - ^1H and ^1H - ^{13}C coupling constants in Hz.

Table 1. List of aldol products

Entry no.	Product structure	Reaction time (h)	Yield (%)
1a		4	25
1b		6	50
1c		6	30

Table 2. List of Knoevenagel products

Entry no.	Product structure	Reaction time (h)	Yield (%)
2a		12	52
2b		12	48
2c		12	56
2d		12	64
2e		12	41
2f		12	57

General procedure for Aldol (Scheme 1):

To a solution of diisopropylamine (0.08 mL, 0.55 mmol) in 2.0 mL of dry THF was added 2.0 (M) n-BuLi (0.28 mL, 0.55 mmol) at 0°C and the mixture was stirred for 30 min under argon atmosphere. The color of the solution was changed to yellow, the temperature was dropped to -50°C, pyruvaldehyde dimethylacetal (100 mg, 0.46 mmol) dissolved in 1.0 mL of dry THF was added slowly, and the resulting mixture was stirred for 1 h to allow the formation of enolate. Then the aldehyde 1-3 (0.46 mmol) dissolved in 1.5 mL of dry THF was added and the mixture was stirred for an addi-

tional 2–4 h at the same temperature. After completion of the reaction as monitored by TLC, the reaction was quenched with saturated aqueous ammonium chloride solution. The organic and aqueous layers were separated, and the aqueous layer was extracted with ethyl acetate (3×5.0 mL). The combined organic extracts were washed with brine and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulfate. After removal of the solvent under reduced pressure, the crude reaction mixture was purified by flash column chromatography on silica gel (230–400 mesh) using 4% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether to afford the pure unsaturated aldol **1a–1c** as a white to pale white solid.

Analytical data:

4-Hydroxy-1,1-dimethoxy-4-phenylbutan-2-one (1a):

¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.77 (2H, d, *J* 16.1 Hz), 7.58 (2H, m), 7.25 (2H, m), 7.08 (1H, d, *J* 16.1 Hz), 4.73 (2H, s), 3.44 (6H, s); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 193.9, 189.3, 185.0, 145.2, 134.6, 132.9, 130.9, 129.0, 128.2, 120.8, 103.9, 101.5, 94.3, 77.2; LCMS (M+H₂O)+ Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₅O₄.H₂O is 242.2530, Found: 242.2, m.p. 162–164°C; *R*_f 0.5 (20% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether).

4-Hydroxy-1,1-dimethoxy-4-pyridylbutan-2-one (1b):

¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 8.92 (1H, s), 8.60 (1H, s), 8.09 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.41 (1H, d, *J* 12.5 Hz), 6.13 (1H, s), 4.50 (1H, s), 3.28 (6H, s); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 186.8, 181.5, 150.9, 148.0, 135.7, 134.1, 123.4, 103.4, 92.2, 53.1, 40.1; LCMS (ESI) (M+H)⁺ Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₅NO₄ is 224.3863, Found: 224.40. *R*_f 0.13 (20% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether).

4-Hydroxy-1,1-dimethoxy-4-(2-nitrophenyl)butan-2-one (1c):

¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.92 (1H, d, *J* 7.7 Hz), 7.83 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.75 (1H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz), 7.51 (1H, s), 5.69 (1H, s), 5.50 (1H, s), 4.62 (2H, s), 3.29 (6H, s); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 193.2, 140.4, 133.6, 132.0, 130.9, 130.6, 129.2, 128.4, 128.4, 125.7, 125.0, 124.2, 103.9, 67.3, 54.8, 29.0; LCMS (M+H₂O)+ Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₅NO₆ is 287.0899, Found: 287.4.

General procedure for the synthesis of α-arylmethylidene-β-diketones (Scheme 2):

To a solution of L-proline (0.33 mmol) in 15.0 mL dry DMSO was added aldehyde (1.0 mmol) and stirred for 8–10 min, at room temperature then acetyl acetone (1.2 mmol)

was added slowly into it at the same temperature and stirred for 12–14 h. After completion of the reaction (monitored by TLC), 20.0 mL ethyl acetate was added into the reaction mixture and was stirred for 8–10 min. The reaction mixture was quenched with cold water. The organic and aqueous layers were separated, and the aqueous layer was extracted with ethyl acetate (3×15.0 mL), washed with brine and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. After removal of the solvent under reduced pressure, the crude reaction mixture was purified by flash column chromatography on silica gel (230–400 mesh) using 6% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether to afford compound **2a-2f**.

3-(2-Chlorobenzylidene)pentane-2,4-dione (2a):

^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz): δ (ppm): 7.34 (1H, s), 7.33 (1H, t, J 1.2 Hz), 7.26 (2H, d, J 18.8 Hz), 7.22 (1H, d, J 18.7 Hz), 2.16 (3H, s), 2.03 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz): δ (ppm): 27.0, 31.9, 77.3, 130.3, 130.5, 131.7, 134.6, 196.6, 204.4; HRMS: $(\text{M}+\text{H})^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClO}_2$ is 223.0448. Found: 223.1330.

3-(2-Bromobenzylidene)pentane-2,4-dione (2b):

^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz): δ (ppm): 7.31 (1H, s), 7.30 (1H, t, J 7.7 Hz), 7.29 (2H, d, J 7.8 Hz), 7.29 (1H, d, J 7.7 Hz), 2.45 (3H, s), 2.14 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz): δ (ppm): 27.02, 31.91, 77.35, 124.56, 128.11, 130.61, 131.76, 133.42, 139.25, 144.56, 196.57, 204.27; HRMS: $(\text{M}+\text{H})^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{BrO}_2$ is 268.1185. Found: 268.1312.

3-(Pyridin-2-ylmethylene)pentane-2,4-dione (2c):

^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz): δ (ppm): 10.02 (1H, s), 9.12 (1H, t, J 2.4 Hz), 8.62 (2H, d, J 16.5 Hz), 8.81 (1H, d, J 16.4 Hz), 2.16 (9H, s), 2.34 (8H, s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz): δ (ppm): 21.2, 25.02, 77.04, 124.01, 129.22, 145.00, 191.03, 196.47, 204.85; HRMS: $(\text{M}+\text{H})^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_2$ is 189.0712. Found: 189.0910.

3-(Quinoxalin-2-ylmethylene)pentane-2,4-dione (2d):

^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz): δ (ppm): 9.17 (1H, s), 8.13 (2H, m), 7.78 (2H, m), 5.57 (1H, s), 3.50 (6H, s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz): δ (ppm): 27.0, 31.9, 77.3, 130.3, 130.5, 131.7, 134.6, 196.6, 204.4; HRMS: $(\text{M}+\text{H})^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ is 241.2573; Found: 241.2480 $(\text{M}+\text{H})^+$; HRMS: $(\text{M}+\text{H})^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ is 241.08, Found: 241.1.

3-(Anthracene-2-ylmethylene)pentane-2,4-dione (2e):

^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz): δ (ppm): 8.46 (2H, d), 8.00 (2H, m), 7.96 (2H, m), 7.55 (4H, m), 2.59 (3H, s), 1.60 (3H,

s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz): δ (ppm): 28.4, 30.9, 77.4, 125.5, 126.0, 127.1, 129.3, 140.0, 167.2; HRMS: M^+ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ is 288.12. Found: 311.0 $(\text{M}+\text{Na})^+$; HRMS: $(\text{M}+\text{H})^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ is 289.3318, Found: 289.351.

3-(Pyrene-2-ylmethylene)pentane-2,4-dione (2f):

^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz): δ (ppm): 8.70 (1H, s), 8.31 (5H, m), 8.21 (3H, m), 8.12 (2H, d, J 8.2 Hz), 2.56 (3H, s), 2.07 (3H, s); HRMS: $(\text{M}+\text{H})^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ is 313.3612. Found: 313.36.

Crystal data:

The molecular structure is shown in Fig. 1. The pyrene ring system is essentially planar with a maximum deviation of 0.034 (2) Å at atom C5. In the crystal (Fig. 2, Supporting information), molecules are linked into inversion dimers by pairs of C16-H16A \cdots O1 hydrogen bonds (Table 2, Supporting information), generating twenty two-membered R22(22) ring motifs. These adjacent dimer molecules are further connected via intermolecular C5-H5A \cdots O2 hydrogen bonds into ladder-style chains along the [100] which consists of twenty two-membered $R_4^4(2,2)$ ring motifs. Short intermolecular dis-

Fig. 1. The molecular structure of **2e** showing 50% probability displacement ellipsoids for non-H atoms and the atom-numbering scheme.

tances between the centroids the benzene rings [(C1-C3/C8-C10) and (C9-C14) rings = 3.5829(9) Å and (C7-C9/C14-C16) and (C9-C14) rings = 3.6130(9) Å] indicate the existence of $\pi \cdots \pi$ interactions. The crystal structure is further consolidated by C4-H4A \cdots Cg1 interactions, where Cg1 is the centroid of C3-C8 benzene ring.

Conclusion

To conclude, we have here reported C-C bond formation reaction sequences for the diketone synthesis of highly functionalized aromatic derivatives specially having benzylic hydroxyl group which are unstable and susceptible to dehydration. The reaction was generalized for the starting pre-

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cursors, containing aromatic groups to afford the corresponding α -arylmethylidene β -diketone products from acetyl acetone and from corresponding aldol reaction of pyruvaldehyde dimethyl acetal in one step.

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References and notes

- (a) D. Enders and T. Gasperi, *Chem. Commun.*, 2007, 88; (b) B. Staniszewski and W. Urbaniak, *Chemical Papers*, 2009, **63**(2), 212.
- J. Kofoed, T. Darbre and J. L. Reymond, *Chem. Commun.*, 2006, 1482.
- R. F. Lopez, J. Kofoed, M. Machuqueiro and T. Darbre, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2005, 5268.
- M. K. Zhu, X. Y. Xu and L. Z. Gong, *Adv. Synth. Catal.*, 2008, **350**, 1390.
- D. Enders and C. Grondal, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2005, **44**, 1210.
- D. Enders, C. Grondal, M. Vrettou and G. Raabe, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2005, **44**, 4079.
- C. Grondal and D. Enders, *Adv. Synth. Catal.*, 2007, **349**, 694.
- C. Grondal and D. Enders, *Tetrahedron*, 2006, **62**, 329.
- (a) M. D. Chappell and R. L. Halcomb, *Org. Lett.*, 2000, **2**, 2003; (b) M. Warwel and W. D. Fessner, *Synlett*, 2002, 2104; (c) M. G. Banwell, N. L. Hungerford and K. A. Jolliffe, *Org. Lett.*, 2004, **6**, 2737.
- (a) L. S. Li and Y. L. Wu, *Curr. Org. Chem.*, 2003, **7**, 447; (b) B. G. Kim, U. Schilde and Y. Linker, *Synthesis*, 2005, 1507; (c) M. S. M. Timmer, A. Adibekian and P. H. Seeberger, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2005, **44**, 7605.
- C. H. Wong and G. M. Whitesides, "Tetrahedron Organic Chemistry Series", Pergamon, Oxford, 1994, **12**.
- (a) T. Ogawa, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1994, **23**, 397; (b) S. J. Danishefsky and M. T. Bilodeau, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1996, **35**, 1380.
- (a) V. Kikelj, R. Plantier-Royon and C. Portella, *Synthesis*, 2006, 1200; (b) H. Tanaka, D. Takahashi and T. Takahashi, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2006, **45**, 770.
- (a) B. Staniszewski and W. Urbaniak, *Chemical Papers*, 2009, **63**, 212; (b) K. T. Mahmudov, A. M. Maharramov, R. A. Aliyeva, I. A. Aliyev, R. K. Askerov, R. Batmaz, M. N. Kopylovich and A. J. L. Pombeiro, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A: Chem.*, 2011, **219**, 159.
- (a) H. Yang, X. Zhang, S. Li, X. Wang and J. Ma, *RSC Adv.*, 2014, **4**, 9292; (b) Md A. S. Khan, J. Zhang, K. Das Sarma and B. Ganguly, *RSC Adv.*, 2012, **2**, 8460; (c) G. Devi Yadav and S. Singh, *RSC Adv.*, 2016, **6**, 100459; (d) A. Kumar and S. S. Chimni, *RSC Adv.*, 2012, **2**, 9748; (e) M. Gangar, A. Ittuveetil, S. Goyal, A. Pal, M. Harikrishnan and V. A. Nair, *RSC Adv.*, 2016, **6**, 102116.
- (a) E. Knoevenagel, *Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 2585; (b) Ce. Su, Z. C. Chen and Q. G. Zheng, *Synthesis*, 2003, 555; (c) A. V. Narsaiah, A. K. Basak, B. Visali and K. Nagaiah, *Synth. Commun.*, 2004, **34**, 2893.
- (a) L. F. Tietze and U. Beifuss, *Comprehensive Organic Synthesis*, 1991, **2**, 341.
- S. P. Goswami, S. Chakraborty, S. Paul, S. Halder, S. Panja and S. K. Mukhopadhyay, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2014, **12**, 2981.
- (a) E. Knoevenagel, *Berichte*, 1898, **31**, 2585; (b) M. K. Ghorai, S. Halder and R. K. Das, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2010, **75**, 7061.
- (a) G. Li, J. Xiao and W. Zhang, *Green Chem.*, 2012, **14**, 2234; (b) E. Priede, S. Brica, E. Bakis, N. Udris and A. Zicmanis, *New J. Chem.*, 2015, **39**, 9132; (c) S. Zhao, X. Wang and L. Zhang, *RSC Adv.*, 2013, **3**, 11691.

